

A one-pot synthesis of alkyl 5-amino-2-mercaptothiazole-4-carboxylates and sulphur-Claisen type rearrangement reactions of the corresponding *S*-allyl/propargyl compounds[†]

Sibdas Ray* and Sukla Ghosh

Department of Chemistry, University of Calcutta, University College of Science, Kolkata-700 009, India

E-mail : sibdas02@yahoo.co.in

Manuscript received 5 September 2003

Alkyl 5-amino-2-mercaptothiazole-4-carboxylates (**5**) have been prepared in a one-pot synthesis by the action of hydrogen sulfide on a mixture of alkyl 2-oximino-2-cyanoacetate and trialkyl orthoformate in pyridine; reduction of the oximino group to imino followed by its trapping with trialkyl orthoformate has been instrumental. *S*-Alkylation of **5** with (ethenyl/ethynyl)methyl bromides has been performed under phase-transfer catalysed conditions avoiding any possible ring-transformation reaction. Thermal 'sulphur to nitrogen' rearrangement of ethyl 5-amino-2-allylmercaptothiazole-4-carboxylate (**12b**) has furnished 5-amino-3-allyl-4-ethoxycarbonylthiazole-2(*3H*)-thione (**15**); addition of AIBN has lowered the reaction-temperature and improved the yield. Similar rearrangement of ethyl 5-amino-2-propargylmercaptothiazole-4-carboxylate (**14b**) has furnished 5-methylpyrrolo[3,2-*d*]thiazole-2(*2H,4H,6aH*)-thione (**17**) and 3*a*-ethoxycarbonyl-5-methylpyrrolo[3,2-*d*]thiazole-2(*2H,3H,3aH*)-thione (**16**); addition of AIBN has improved the yield of **17**.

In nature, the role of a few natural thiazole compounds is of fundamental importance in primary metabolic reactions. The thiazolium moiety of thiamine pyrophosphate, the essential coenzyme in the decarboxylation of pyruvate to acetaldehyde, reflects the low activation energy associated with the thermodynamically stable ylide in the transition state at physiological pH and hence is of great biological importance¹, a great deal of research has been devoted to the synthetic analogues of this thiazolium moiety. Antibiotics *Ulicyclamide*^{2a} and *Microcyclamide*^{2b} and a novel cytotoxic heptapeptide, *Leucamide*,³ may be mentioned among the important natural macrocycles containing thiazole ring. Penicillins constitute an important group of compounds containing reduced thiazole units. Recently bithiazole compounds have been important synthetic targets⁴.

AICA-ribotide, [5-amino-1-(5-phospho- β -D-ribofuranosyl)imidazole-4-carboxamide], has early been established as an important intermediate in the *de novo* biosynthetic pathway of purine nucleotides⁵. As congeners of AICA, 5-aminothiazole-4-carboxamide and its analogues have become compounds of interest. Thiazole compounds with amino or mercapto groups at C₂/C₅ positions are conspicuous for ring-transformations and similar reactions and offer complicated and interesting situation for investigations. Several reviews in the field of thiazole have been published⁶.

Synthesis of ethyl 5-aminothiazole-4-carboxylate (**1**) or its amide, 5-aminothiazole-4-carboxamide (**2**) was performed by reaction of sodium dithioformate with ethyl 2-amino-2-cyanoacetate (**3**) or 2-amino-2-cyanoacetamide (**4**)⁷. Reaction of **3** and **4** with carbon disulphide to produce ethyl 5-amino-2-mercaptothiazole-4-carboxylate (**5b**) and 5-amino-2-mercaptothiazole-4-carboxamide (**6**) respectively were reported⁷. Later, **1** was prepared from *N*-(ethoxycarbonylcyanomethyl)formimidate (**7**) by reaction with hydrogen sulphide in pyridine; **7**, in turn, was generated from **3** and ethyl orthoformate⁸. In the above synthetic procedure, **3** was prepared by reduction of ethyl 2-oximino-2-cyanoacetate (**8b**) with aluminium amalgam and water⁹. Preparation of aluminium amalgam from aluminium foil and aqueous mercuric chloride solution is hazardous and environmentally offensive.

Synthesis of alkyl 5-amino-2-mercaptothiazole-4-carboxylate in a one-pot reaction :

In our attempt to synthesise **5**, it was surmised that reduction of the oximino moiety of alkyl 2-oximino-2-cyanoacetate (**8**) could be performed with hydrogen sulphide, in a one-pot reaction, on a mixture of **8** and alkyl orthoformate in pyridine so that reduction of the oximino moiety would occur in a stepwise manner with initial generation of alkyl 2-imino-2-cyanoacetate (**9**) or alkyl 2-imino-2-thiocarboxamidoacetate (**10**) which should be, in

[†]Dedicated to Professor S. M. Mukherji.

Table 1. (Ethenyl/ethynyl)methylation of **5** under phase transfer catalysed condition (Scheme 2)

Compd.	R ₁	R ₂	M.p.	Yield (%)	δ_{H} of CH ₂ S (J in Hz)	δ_{C} of CH ₂ S	λ_{max} (log ϵ)/ λ_{min} (log ϵ)	M ⁺
12a	CH ₃	Allyl	82–84°	80.0	3.66 (7.0)	38.48	293.5 (3.95)/238.0 (2.99)	–
12b	CH ₃ CH ₂	Allyl	86°	81.5	3.5 (7.0)	38.65	293.5 (4.09)/238.5 (3.3)	244
13a	CH ₃	Cinnamyl	146–147°	40.7	3.8 (7.2)	38.36	293.5 (3.87)/285.5 (3.82); 258.0 (4.04)	–
13b	CH ₃ CH ₃	Cinnamyl	115–116°	37.4	3.74 (7.2)	38.18	294.0 (4.09), 285.5 (4.08), 258.0 (4.26)/291.0 (4.08), 282 (sh), 228.0 (3.79)	–
14a	CH ₃	Propargyl	127°	58.7	3.71 (s)	24.04	293.0 (4.05)/238.0 (3.31)	–
14b	CH ₃ CH ₂	Propargyl	102°	92.7	3.66 (s)	24.10	292.5 (4.09)/237.5 (3.3)	242

Attempt of thermal rearrangement of ethyl 5-amino-2-allylmercaptothiazole-4-carboxylate (**12b**) in bromobenzene has been successful only at a sufficiently high temperature (bath temperature ~265°) and heating at that temperature in a sealed tube for a period of 9 h led to subsequent isolation of 5-amino-3-allyl-4-ethoxycarbonylthiazole-2(3*H*)-thione (**15**, Scheme 3) in only 19.2% yield and the starting material in 72% recovery; similar thermal treatment of ethyl 5-amino-2-cinnamylmercaptothiazole-4-carboxylate (**13b**) in bromobenzene in a sealed tube in an oil bath at a temperature >265° for several hours led to charring and subsequent work up to get some starting material only. This failure of thermal rearrangement of a substrate with unsymmetrical ethenylmethyl moiety debarred us from ascertaining whether a regular [3,3]-sigmatropic change had occurred or a non-thio-Claisen type migration of ethenylmethyl moiety has occurred from 'sulphur to nitrogen' without rearrangement in the ethenylmethyl skeleton; an early report of similar 'sulphur to carbon' migration without rearrangement in the ethenylmethyl moiety is worthy of mention¹³.

Scheme 3

The thermal rearrangement of **12b** in the presence of 20 mole percent of AIBN occurred in refluxing bromobenzene (bath temperature 165°) during a period of 13 h when a mixture of the product (**15**) and the starting material in the ratio of 2 : 3 was worked up. It appears that the radical-initiator has supported the rearrangement and a mechanism involving 'internal radical-capture' (*vide supra*) can not be ruled out. The role of AIBN to generate radical species by

participating in the homolysis of 'carbon to heteroatom' bond is well established¹⁴. The product (**15**) shows the presence of N-CH₂ with signals at δ 5.95 in its ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) and at δ 51.13 in its ¹³C NMR (CDCl₃) spectra; the C₂=S carbon signal is observed at δ 177.34; other signals in its ¹H NMR and ¹³C NMR spectra have been routinely analysed (experimental section).

Thermal rearrangement of ethyl 5-amino-2-propargylmercaptothiazole-4-carboxylate (**14b**) occurred very easily on heating in refluxing bromobenzene for 5 h and, although formation of some tarry material was observed, no starting material was isolated. Two products, namely, 5-methylpyrrolo[3,2-*d*]thiazole-2(2*H*,4*H*,6*aH*) thione (**17**) and 3*a*-ethoxycarbonyl-5-methylpyrrolo[3,2-*d*]thiazole-2(2*H*,3*H*,3*aH*) thione (**16**) were isolated in 11 and 40% respectively; the purification of the latter by preparative TLC on silica gel was needed. It is possible that **17** has been generated out of pyrolytic removal of -CO₂C₂H₅ moiety from **16** in steps. The reaction of **14b** in refluxing bromobenzene in the presence of 20 mole percent of AIBN for 2 h furnished an improved yield of **17** (36.5%); no attempt to isolate **16** has been made during the work-up. A possible course of the thermal change of **14b** is shown in Scheme 4. In its ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) spectrum, **17** shows three singlets at δ 7.26, 5.06 and 2.24 assignable to *H*-6*a*, CH₂ and CH₃ protons respectively; in its ¹³C NMR (CDCl₃) spectrum, the corresponding carbon signals appeared at δ 125.47, 36.22 and 12.77 respectively; singlets in the ¹³C NMR (CDCl₃) spectrum at δ 188.10, 125.47 and 113.10 have been assigned to C-2, C-3*a* and C-5 respectively.

The ¹H NMR spectra of **16** in CDCl₃ and DMSO-*d*₆ solvents differed mutually; the appearance of the ¹H NMR spectrum of **16** taken in CDCl₃ is more simple and a three proton singlet at δ 2.13 assignable to 5-CH₃ and a one-

Scheme 4

proton pair of singlets at δ 6.94 and 7.18 assignable to 4-H have been obtained in the spectrum. The ^1H NMR spectrum of the compound in $\text{DMSO}-d_6$ solvent is much more complex and large number of signals, thronged in the spectrum, may possibly correspond to an equilibrium between **16** and its tautomer and the spectrum could not be analysed to profit. The ^{13}C NMR spectrum of the compound could not be availed of due to its sparse solubility even in $\text{DMSO}-d_6$.

Experimental

The melting points are uncorrected. IR spectra were recorded in KBr pellets on a Perkin-Elmer 782 spectrophotometer and UV spectra of ethanolic solution of the compounds were recorded on a Hitachi U-200 spectrophotometer. The ^1H NMR spectra were run in CDCl_3 (unless otherwise mentioned) on a Bruker AM-300L instrument operating at 300 MHz with TMS as internal standard and the ^{13}C NMR spectra were run in CDCl_3 (unless otherwise mentioned) on the same instrument operating at 75.4 MHz. Silica gel (60–120 mesh) was used for chromatographic purification.

Synthesis of ethyl 5-amino-2-mercaptothiazole-4-carboxylate (5b): Dry hydrogen sulphide gas (dried over an-

hydrous calcium chloride) was passed through a solution of ethyl 2-oximino-2-cyanoacetate (**8b**; 24.0 g, 0.169 mol) and triethyl orthoformate (27.5 g, 0.185 mol) in freshly distilled dry pyridine (50 ml) at 60° (bath-temperature) for a period of 15 h with frequent intermittent swirling. Towards the end of the reaction period (after ~ 13 h), the reaction mixture suddenly assumed a dark colour with massive precipitation of shining crystals of sulphur. The post-reaction mixture was cooled and filtered from the precipitate of sulphur. Pyridine present in the mother liquor was scrupulously removed by repeated trituration of the mother liquor with petroleum ether (15 ml \times 10), removing the upper layer of petroleum ether each time as far as possible by way of pipetting out. This operation finally led to obtainment of a thick semi-crystalline oily material which was then cooled and slowly poured into cold water (500 ml) to which concentrated hydrochloric acid (1 ml) had been added. The resulting crude solid was filtered out and triturated with cold aqueous sodium hydroxide solution (10%, 20 ml). The alkaline mixture was filtered and filtrate was acidified with dilute hydrochloric acid to get the title compound. This was crystallized from ethanol to furnish yellow crystalline solid in a yield of 6.55 g (22%), m.p. $180\text{--}182^\circ$.

Characterisation data for 5b: ν_{max} (KBr) 3460 (s), 3300 (s), 1708 (s), 1670 (s), 1590, 1480, 1410, 1380, 1145, 1010, 855 (br), 770 cm^{-1} ; λ_{max} (log ϵ) at 316.0 (4.6) and λ_{min} (log ϵ) at 256.5 (3.79) nm; δ 1.22 and 1.25 (3H, pair of partially overlapping t, J 7.1 Hz, OCH_2CH_3), 4.18 and 4.21 (2H, pair of partially overlapping q, J , 7.1 Hz, OCH_2CH_3), 7.64 and 7.75 (2H, pair of broad s, $-\text{NH}_2$); δ_c 188.42 (s, 2-C), 163.33 and 161.39 (both s, $-\text{CO}_2\text{Et}$ and 5-C), 119.92 (s, 4-C), 59.56 (t, OCH_2-), 14.54 (q, OCH_2CH_3); m/z 204 (base peak, $\text{M}^{+\bullet}$), 187 (6.5%, $\text{MH}-\text{NH}_2$), 176 (10%, $\text{M}-\text{C}_2\text{H}_4$), 158 (86%), 130 (31%) (Found: C, 35.46; H, 4.11; N 13.57. $\text{C}_6\text{H}_8\text{N}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_2$ requires: C, 35.29; H, 3.92; N 13.73%).

Synthesis of methyl 5-amino-2-mercaptothiazole-4-carboxylate (5a): The title compound was synthesized from methyl 2-oximino-2-cyanoacetate (**8a**; 26.4 g, 0.206 mol) and trimethyl orthoformate (22.3 g, 0.21 mol) in a procedure essentially similar to what was followed for the synthesis of its ethyl ester analogue (**5b**) from ethyl 2-oximino-2-cyanoacetate (**8b**) and triethyl orthoformate, as reddish brown solid, recrystallisable from ethanol in an yield of 7.4 g (19.3%); m.p. $190\text{--}191^\circ$.

Characterisation data for 5a: ν_{max} (KBr) 3420 (s), 3390 (s), 3080 (br), 1650 (s, C=O str.), 1600 (s), 1535 (s), 1505 (s), 1435, 1380 (s), 1285 (s), 1190 (s), 1140 (s), 1030 (s), 980 (s), 860 (s), 765 (s), 730 (s), 500 (s) cm^{-1} ; λ_{max}

(log ϵ) at 316.5 (4.51) and λ_{\min} (log ϵ) at 256.0 (3.72) nm. Lack of solubility of the compound even in a highly polar solvent like DMSO- d_6 baffled attempts of scanning its ^1H NMR and ^{13}C NMR spectra (Found : C, 31.34; H, 3.35; N, 14.50. $\text{C}_5\text{H}_6\text{N}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_2$ requires : C, 31.58; H, 3.16; N 14.74%).

Dethiation of ethyl 5-amino-2-mercaptothiazole-4-carboxylate (5b) with Raney nickel to obtain ethyl 5-aminothiazole-4-carboxylate (1) : The compound, synthesised from ethyl 2-oximino-2-cyanoacetate, triethyl orthoformate and hydrogen sulphide in pyridine and finally proved to be **5b** (1.0 g), was heated under reflux in dry ethanol (20 ml) with freshly prepared Raney nickel (3 g) for half an hour and the post-reaction mixture was filtered hot. Solvent was removed from the filtrate and the resulting crude residue was put to column-chromatography on silica-gel. Elution, initially with chloroform-petroleum ether mixture, furnished ethyl 5-aminothiazole-4-carboxylate (**1**) in an yield of 0.24 g (29%) followed by elution with chloroform containing methanol to offer the starting material (**5b**) in 10% return. Ethyl 5-aminothiazole-4-carboxylate (**1**) is recrystallisable from ethanol; m.p.162–163°. [lit.⁷ m.p. 162–163°].

Characterisation data for 1 : ν_{\max} (KBr) 3370 (s, -NH₂), 3240 (s), 3140 (s), 2990 (s), 1660 (s, C=O str.), 1620 (s), 1500 (s), 1460 (s), 1435 (s), 1405 (s), 1370 (s), 1205 (s), 1155 (s), 1105 (s), 1000 (s), 890 (s), 830 (s), 760 (s), 730 (s) cm^{-1} ; λ_{\max} (log ϵ) at 278.0 (4.16), 209.0 (4.55) and λ_{\min} (log ϵ) at 230.5 (0.39) nm; δ (DMSO- d_6) 1.22 (3H, J 7.1 Hz, OCH₂CH₃), 4.16 (2H, q, J 7.1 Hz, OCH₂CH₃), 7.29 (2H, broad s, -NH₂), 7.92 (1H, s, H -2); δ_c (DMSO- d_6) 163.84 (s, CO₂Et), 160.46 (s, 5-C), 135.43 (d, 2-C), 120.31 (s, 4-C), 59.32 (t, OCH₂-), 14.53 (q, OCH₂CH₃); m/z 172 (73%, M⁺), 144 (17%), 126 (base peak), 100 (67%). Crystallographic studies : ORTEP diagram is shown in Fig. 1 (Found : C, 41.49; H, 4.43; N, 16.46. $\text{C}_6\text{H}_8\text{N}_2\text{O}_2\text{S}$ requires : C, 41.86; H, 4.65; N, 16.27%).

Fig. 1. ORTEP diagram of ethyl 5-aminothiazole-4-carboxylate (**1**).

General procedure for (ethenyl/ethynyl)methylation of ethyl/methyl 5-amino-2-mercaptothiazole-4-carboxylates (5b/5a) with (ethenyl/ethynyl)methyl bromides under phase-transfer catalysed condition : To a well-stirred solution of ethyl/methyl 5-amino-2-mercaptothiazole-4-carboxylate (0.01 mol) in cold dichloromethane (100 ml), provided with an ice-salt bath, was added a solution of sodium bicarbonate (0.03 mol) in cold water (50 ml), followed by benzyltriethylammonium chloride (2.27 g, 0.01 mol) in cold water (10 ml). A solution of (ethenyl/ethynyl)methyl bromide (0.015 mol) in dichloromethane (10 ml) was added dropwise to the well-stirred reaction mixture during 30 min and then stirring was continued for a period of 5 h for the purpose of completion of the reaction. The organic layer was then removed and the aqueous layer was extracted with dichloromethane (2 \times 10 ml). The combined dichloromethane-extract was washed with cold water (2 \times 10 ml) and dried over activated sodium sulphate. The solvent was then removed from the dried extract and the residue was subjected to separation/purification with the help of column-chromatography on silica-gel by elution with chloroform-petroleum ether mixture.

Methyl 5-amino-2-allylmercaptothiazole-4-carboxylate (12a) : White crystalline solid, yield 80%; m.p. 82–84°; ν_{\max} (KBr) 3400 (s, -NH₂, str.), 3270 (s), 1690 (s, C=O str.), 1618 (s), 1510, 1449, 1418, 1392, 1280, 1115, 1010, 910, 870 (br), 780, 725, 620, 565, 505 cm^{-1} ; λ_{\max} (log ϵ) at 293.5 (3.95) and λ_{\min} (log ϵ) at 238.0 (2.98) nm; δ 3.66 (2H, d, J 7.0 Hz, -SCH₂), 3.89 (3H, s, -OCH₃), 5.07–5.20 (2H, complex m, =CH₂), 5.83–5.97 (1H, complex m, =CH), 6.11 (2H, broad s, -NH₂); δ_c 164.35 (s, CO₂Me), 160.81 (s, 5-C), 143.52 (s, 2-C), 132.70 (d, CH=), 122.04 (s, 4-C), 118.63 (t, =CH₂), 51.38 (q, OCH₃), 38.48 (t, SCH₂) (Found : C, 41.51; H, 4.20; N, 12.25. $\text{C}_8\text{H}_{10}\text{N}_2\text{O}_2\text{S}_2$ requires : C, 41.74; H, 4.35; N, 12.17%).

Ethyl 5-amino-2-allylmercaptothiazole-4-carboxylate (12b) : White crystalline solid, yield 81.5%; m.p. 86°; ν_{\max} (KBr) 3440 (br, -NH₂, str.) 1700 (s, C=O str.), 1675 (s), 1610 (s), 1500, 1405, 1372, 1260, 1100, 1000, 912, 765, 725 cm^{-1} ; λ_{\max} (log ϵ) at 293.0 (4.09) and λ_{\min} (log ϵ) at 238.5 (3.30) nm; δ 1.31 (3H, t, J 7.2 Hz, OCH₂CH₃), 3.57 (2H, d, J 7.0 Hz, -SCH₂), 4.29 (2H, q, J 7.2 Hz, -OCH₂), 5.03–5.15 (2H, complex m, =CH₂), 5.75–5.89 (1H, complex m, =CH-), 6.11(2H, broad s, -NH₂); δ_c 164.12 (s, CO₂Et), 160.71 (s, 5-C), 143.36 (s, 2-C), 132.70 (d, -CH=), 122.20 (s, 4-C), 118.83 (t, =CH₂), 60.56 (t, OCH₂-), 38.65 (t, SCH₂), 14.47 (q, OCH₂CH₃); m/z 244 (68%, M⁺), 229 (base peak, M-CH₃), 203 (42%), 170 (14%, MH-SC₃H₅), 100 (67%) (Found : C, 44.01; H, 4.98; N, 11.26.

$C_6H_{12}N_2O_2S_2$ requires : C, 44.26; H, 4.92; N 11.48%.

Methyl 5-amino-2-cinnamylmercaptothiazole-4-carboxylate (13a) : White crystalline solid, yield 40.7%; m.p. 146–147°; ν_{\max} (KBr) 3400 (s, $-NH_2$, str.), 3220 (s), 3120, 1670 (s, C=O str.), 1584, 1475, 1453, 1380, 1280, 1260, 1100, 990, 950, 760, 745, 695 cm^{-1} ; λ_{\max} (log ϵ) at 294.0 (4.09), 285.5 (4.11), 258.0 (4.26) and λ_{\min} (log ϵ) at 291.5 (4.07), 282.0 (4.09), 228.0 (3.79) nm; δ 3.81 (2H, d, J 7.0 Hz, $-SCH_2$), 3.84 (3H, s, $-OCH_3$), 6.09 (2H, broad s, NH_2), 6.25 (1H, complex m, $=CHCH_2-$), 6.49 (1H, d, J 15.6 Hz, $=CHPh$), 7.21–7.35 (5H, complex m, C_6H_5); δ_c 164.29 (s, CO_2Me), 134.17 (d, $CH_2CH=$), 128.55 (d, two *ortho* C of Ph gr.), 127.8 (d, *para* C of Ph gr.), 126.52 (d, two *meta* C of Ph gr.), 124.12 (d, Ph-CH=), 51.38 (q, $-OCH_3$), 39.36 (t, $-SCH_2$) (Found : C, 54.71; H, 4.47; N, 9.02. $C_{14}H_{14}N_2O_2S_2$ requires : C, 54.90; H, 4.58; N, 9.15%).

Ethyl 5-amino-2-cinnamylmercaptothiazole-4-carboxylate (13b) : White crystalline solid, yield 37.4%; m.p. 115–116°; ν_{\max} (KBr) 3380 (br, $-NH_2$, str.), 3220 (s), 1680, (s, C=O str.), 1595, 1505, 1410, 1270, 1110, 1015, 980, 905, 755, 705 cm^{-1} ; λ_{\max} (log ϵ) at 293.5 (3.87), 285.5 (3.82), 258.0 (4.04) and λ_{\min} (log ϵ) at 291.5 (3.86), 282.0 (3.85), 228.5 (3.55) nm; δ 1.33 (3H, t, J 7.1 Hz, $-OCH_2CH_3$), 3.74 (2H, d, J 7.2 Hz, $-SCH_2$), 4.31 (2H, q, J 7.1 Hz, $-OCH_2$), 6.21 (1H, complex m, $=CHCH_2-$), 6.46 (1H, d, J 15.6 Hz, $=CHPh$), 7.18–7.32 (5H, complex m, C_6H_5); δ_c 163.91 (s, CO_2Et), 133.89 (d, $CH_2CH=$), 128.34 (d, two *ortho* C of Ph gr.), 127.58 (d, *para* C of Ph gr.), 126.31 (d, two *meta* C of Ph gr.), 124.02 (d, Ph-CH=), 60.56 (t, $-OCH_2$), 38.18 (t, $-SCH_2$), 14.47 (q, $-OCH_2CH_3$) (Found : C, 56.10; H, 4.78; N, 8.56. $C_{15}H_{16}N_2O_2S_2$ requires : C, 56.25; H, 5.00; N 8.75%).

Methyl 5-amino-2-propargylmercaptothiazole-4-carboxylate (14a) : White crystalline solid, yield 58.7%; m.p. 127°; ν_{\max} (KBr) 3400 (s, $-NH_2$), 3270 (s), 1690, (s, C=O str.), 1618 (s), 1510, 1449, 1418, 1392, 1280, 1150, 1010, 910, 870, 780, 725, 625, 565, 505 cm^{-1} ; λ_{\max} (log ϵ) at 293.5 (4.05) and λ_{\min} (log ϵ) at 238.0 (3.31) nm; δ 2.30 (1H, s, $\equiv CH$), 3.71 (2H, s, $-SCH_2$), 3.88 (3H, s, $-OCH_3$), 6.17 (2H, broad s, NH_2); δ_c 78.72 (s, $CH_2C\equiv$), 72.85 (d, $\equiv CH$), 51.56 (q, $-OCH_3$), 24.04 (t, $-SCH_2$) (Found : C, 41.80; H, 3.28; N, 12.39. $C_8H_8N_2O_2S_2$ requires : C, 41.92; H, 3.49; N, 12.28%).

Ethyl 5-amino-2-propargylmercaptothiazole-4-carboxylate (14b) : White crystalline solid, yield 92.7%; m.p. 102°; ν_{\max} (KBr) 3420 (s, $-NH_2$), 3290 (s), 3160 (s), 1680 (s, C=O str.), 1600 (s), 1485 (s), 1440, 1415, 1265 (s), 1110 (br), 1010 (s), 780, 670 (s) cm^{-1} ; λ_{\max} (log ϵ) at 292.5 (4.09) and λ_{\min} (log ϵ) at 237.5 (3.34) nm; δ 1.32 (3H, t, J

7.2 Hz, OCH_2CH_3), 2.25 (1H, t, J 2.7 Hz, $\equiv CH$), 3.68 (2H, d, J 2.7 Hz, $-SCH_2$), 4.31 (2H, q, J 7.2 Hz, OCH_2), 6.16 (2H, broad s, NH_2); m/z 242 ($M^{+\bullet}$, base peak), 213 (27%), 203 (98%), 196 (71%), 170 (28%), 127 (33%), 100 (34%) (Found : C, 44.84; H, 3.90; N, 11.76. $C_9H_{10}N_2O_2S_2$ requires : C, 44.63; H, 4.13; N, 11.57%).

Thermal rearrangement of ethyl 5-amino-2-allylmercaptothiazole-4-carboxylate (12b) : obtainment of ethyl 5-amino-3-allyl-4-ethoxycarbonylthiazole-2(3H)-thione (15) : Ethyl 5-amino-2-allylmercaptothiazole-4-carboxylate (**12b**) (250 mg, 1.02 mmol) in dry bromobenzene (10 ml) was heated in a sealed-tube in an oil-bath (bath temperature -265°) for 9 h. Solvent was removed from the post-reaction mixture under reduced pressure and the residue was subjected to column-chromatographic separation on silica-gel with petroleum ether-chloroform mixture of gradually increasing polarity. Starting material (**12b**) was isolated in 72% (180 mg) return with 1 : 1 mixture of chloroform-petroleum ether as the eluent. Subsequently the title compound, ethyl 5-amino-3-allyl-4-ethoxycarbonylthiazole-2(3H)-thione (**15**) was separated by elution with chloroform in an yield of 48 mg (19.2%) as a reddish viscous oil, turning to a low melting solid on keeping; melting point could not be noted; ν_{\max} (KBr) 3420 (s, $-NH_2$), 2290 (s), 1680 (s, C=O str.), 1590 (s), 1560 (s), 1425 (s), 1380 (s), 1340 (s), 1265 (s), 1220 (s), 1110 (s), 1025 (s), 970 (s), 810 (s) cm^{-1} ; δ 5.06–5.17 (4H, complex m, NCH_2 and $=CH_2$), 5.77–5.88 (1H, complex, m, $-CH=$), 5.95 (2H, broad s, NH_2), 4.27 (2H, q, J 7.1 Hz, OCH_2-), 1.30 (3H, t, J 7.1 Hz, OCH_2CH_3); δ_c 177.34 (s, 2-C), 151.94 and 159.29 (both s, 4-C and 5-C), 131.62 (d, $=CH-$), 117.83 (t, $=CH_2$), 61.01 (t, OCH_2-), 51.13 (t, NCH_2-), 14.30 (q, OCH_2CH_3) (Found : C, 44.57; H, 4.81; N, 11.15. $C_9H_{12}N_2O_2S_2$ requires : C, 44.26; H, 4.92; N, 11.48%).

Thermal rearrangement of ethyl 5-amino-2-allylmercaptothiazole-4-carboxylate (12b) in presence of azidodiisobutyronitrile (AIBN) as the radical initiator : Thermal rearrangement of ethyl 5-amino-2-allylmercaptothiazole-4-carboxylate (**12b**) was conducted in the presence of 20 mole percent of AIBN in refluxing dry bromobenzene (bath temperature 165°) for a period of 13 h. The compounds, isolated in a procedure essentially as above, were ethyl 5-amino-3-allyl-4-ethoxycarbonylthiazole-2(3H)-thione (**15**) and the starting material (**12b**) in 2 : 3 molar ratio, yield of **15** was 31%. The two compounds were identified by spectroscopic analysis (IR, UV, 1H NMR, ^{13}C NMR etc.) in the usual way.

Thermal rearrangement of ethyl 5-amino-2-propargylmercaptothiazole-4-carboxylate (14b) : obtainment of

3a-ethoxycarbonyl-5-methylpyrrolo[3,2-d]thiazole-2(2H,3H,3aH)-thione (16) and 5-methylpyrrolo[3,2-d]thiazole-2(2H,4H,6aH)-thione (17) : Ethyl 5-amino-2-propargylmercaptothiazole-4-carboxylate (14b) (5.0 g, 0.020 mol) was heated under reflux in dry bromobenzene (50 ml) for 5 h using an oil-bath (bath temperature ~165°). Solvent was removed from the post-reaction mixture under reduced pressure and the solid was subjected to column-chromatography on silica-gel; at first 5-methylpyrrolo[2,3-d]thiazole-2(2H,4H,6aH)-thione (17) was eluted with chloroform-petroleum ether (7 : 3, v/v). Subsequently, 3a-ethoxycarbonyl-5-methylpyrrolo[3,2-d]thiazole-2(2H,3H,3aH)-thione (16) was taken out in a very crude form with chloroform containing 5% methanol as eluent; this crude material was purified by preparative TLC on silica-gel using chloroform containing 2% methanol as eluent .

5-Methylpyrrolo[3,2-d]thiazole-2(2H,4H,6aH)-thione (17) was obtained in an yield of 0.37 g (11%), it is recrystallised from chloroform-petroleum ether mixture as colourless crystalline solid; m.p. 105°; ν_{\max} (KBr) 3100, 1610, 1440 (s), 1410 (s), 1350 (br), 1255 (s), 1230, 1170, 1110 (s), 930, 790 (s), 710 (s) cm^{-1} ; λ_{\max} (log ϵ) at 320.5 (4.1) and λ_{\min} (log ϵ) at 274.0 (2.98) nm; δ 2.24 (3H, s, CH₃), 5.06 (2H, s, CH₂), 7.26 (1H, s, H-6a); δ_{c} 188.10 (s, 2-C), 125.47 (s, 3a-C), 113.10 (s, 5-C), 125.47 (d, J 185.5 Hz, 6a-C), 36.2 (t, J 149.5 Hz, 4-C), 12.77 (q, J 131.5 Hz, CH₃); *m/z* 170 (M⁺, base peak), 143 (30%, M-C₂H₃), 129 (26%, M-CH₃CN), 86 (32%) (Found : C, 42.08; H, 3.38; N, 16.20. C₆H₆N₂S₂ requires : C, 42.35; H, 3.53; N, 16.47%).

3a-Ethoxycarbonyl-5-methylpyrrolo[3,2-d]thiazole-2(2H,3H, 3aH)-thione (16) was obtained in an yield of 2.09 g (42%) as yellow amorphous (microcrystalline) solid, recrystallisable from ethanol, m.p. 265° (dec); ν_{\max} (KBr) 3450 (s, -NH), 3090 (s), 1685 (s, C=O str.), 1615 (s), 1575 (s), 1520, 1405, 1370, 1335 (s), 1255 (s), 1205 (s), 1120, 1070 (s), 1040, 815 (br) cm^{-1} ; λ_{\max} (log ϵ) at 375.0 (2.75), 321.5 (3.15), 282 (5.18), 273 (3.19) and λ_{\min} (log ϵ) at 255.5 (2.68), 302.0 (3.00), 279 (3.7) nm; δ 1.06 and 1.13 (3H in total, each t, J 7.1 Hz, OCH₂CH₃), 2.13 (3H, s, 5-CH₃), 3.95 and 3.98 (2H in total, m and q respectively, J 7.1 Hz for q, OCH₂CH₃), 6.94 and 7.18 (1H in total, both s, H-4); ¹³C NMR could not be availed of due to lack of sufficient solubility even in DMSO-*d*₆.

Acknowledgement

We thank Mr. A. Acharya for ¹H NMR and ¹³C NMR spectral measurements and Dr. T. Banerjee, Department of Physics, University of Calcutta, for X-ray crystallographic analysis. One of the authors (S.G.) is thankful to U.G.C., New Delhi and C.S.I.R., New Delhi for awarding a research fellowship.

References

1. R. Breslow, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1958, **80**, 3719.
2. (a) P. Wipf, *Chem. Rev.*, 1995, **95**, 2116; R. A. Agabaria and D. Gill, *J. Photochem. Photobiol. A. Chem.*, 1994, **78**, 161; (b) *Chem. Abstr.*, 1992, Index guide (1323G), *Micrococcin P* [1392-46-7].
3. S. Kehraus, G. M. König and A. D. Wright, *J. Org. Chem.*, 2002, **67**, 4989.
4. A. Noack and H. Hartmann, *Tetrahedron*, 2002, **58**, 2137; J. Schumann, A. Kanitz and H. Hartmann, *Synthesis*, 2002, 1268.
5. S. C. Hartmann and J. M. Buchanan, *Ann. Rev. Biochem.*, 1959, **28**, 365.
6. (a) J. V. Mentzer in 'Comprehensive Heterocyclic Chemistry', eds. A. Weissberger and C. W. Rees, Pergamon Press, Oxford-New York, 1984, Vol. 6 (Part 4B), 235-331; (b) D. N. Reinhoudt in 'Advances in Heterocyclic Chemistry', eds. A. R. Kartritsky and A. J. Boulton, Academic Press, New York, 1977, Vol. 21; (c) A. R. Mentzer in 'Thiazole and its Derivatives', in *Chem. Heterocycl. Compd.*, eds. A. Weissberger and E. C. Taylor, John Wiley and Sons, 1979, Vol. 34.
7. A. H. Cook, I. Heilbron and A. Levi, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1947, 1594; A. H. Cook, I. Heilbron and E. Smith, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1949, 1440.
8. A. K. Sen and A. Mukhopadhyay, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1981, **20**, 275.
9. L. H. Smith and P. Yates, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, **76**, 6080.
10. A. Domingues, J. C. Lopez and R. Framco, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1961, **26**, 1612.
11. (a) H. Kwart and J. Schwartz, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1974, **39**, 1575; (b) K. K. Balsubramanian and B. Venugopalan, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1974, 2643, 2645.
12. (a) M. Mizutani, Y. Sanemitsu, Y. Tamaru and Z. I. Yoshida, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1985, **50**, 764; 1983, **48**, 4585; (b) H. Taneka, Y. Banba, M. Mozumi and T. Yamazaki, *Heterocycles*, 1986, **24**, 947.
13. J. Z. Mortense, B. Hedegraad and S.-O. Lawessen, *Tetrahedron*, 1971, **27**, 3831.
14. (a) E. J. Corey and R. H. Wollenberg, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1975, **40**, 2265; *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1974, **96**, 5581; (b) C. Walling and B. B. Jacknow, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1960, **82**, 6108, 6113.

